

Digital Journey: A Narrative Inquiry on Instructional Technology Experiences of English Teachers

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Abstract. This qualitative phenomenological study investigated the lived experiences of ten junior high school English teachers from public secondary schools in the Panabo Central District, Panabo City Division, investigates the personal and professional experiences of English teachers as they integrate instructional technology into their teaching practices. The study employs a narrative inquiry methodology to investigate the ways in which teachers' adoption and adaptation of technology have been influenced by a range of factors, including professional development, mentorship, classroom engagement, and institutional support. It highlights the strategies that teachers use to deal with the difficulties raised by digital instruction, such instructional flexibility and backup planning, the application of effective classroom management and student-centered approaches, and the innovative use of multimedia and gamification to maintain engagement and improve learning outcomes. Emerging from the narratives are core values that shaped teachers' pedagogical identity in the digital landscape: adaptability and flexibility in facing change, creativity and innovation in designing instruction, and heightened sensitivity to learners' needs through individualized and differentiated teaching. This research contributes to a deeper understanding of the dynamic relationship between technology and pedagogy, offering insights into how English teachers navigate and thrive in an increasingly digital educational landscape.

KEY WORDS

1. Narrative inquiry 2. digital journey 3. English education

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1. Introduction

The integration of ICT in English language teaching has brought about substantial changes in how lessons were conducted, promoting a more interactive and engaging learning environment. However, many teachers face serious challenges in utilizing digital technology due to limitations in resources, which affect the overall effectiveness of these tools. These challenges hinder the ability of both teachers and learners to fully take advantage of digital learning, reducing the potential impact of ICT integration in the classroom. Consequently, despite the promise of enhanced educational outcomes, the insufficient support and resources prevents teachers from maximizing the benefits of ICT for language learning. In Nepal, the challenges faced by English language teachers, particularly intensified when digital technology is integrated into the classroom. While effective teaching requires a broad set of competencies, including language

proficiency, pedagogical reasoning, and contextual knowledge, many teachers struggle to bridge the gap between their theoretical understanding and the practical application of these competencies, especially when using ICT (Laudari Maher, 2019). In Northern California, the digital divide presents a distinct barrier to ensuring equitable access to these digital instructional materials for all learners. Inadequate infrastructure and limited access to digital devices and high-speed internet often prevent English teachers, particularly in underserved communities, from fully benefiting from technology-enhanced learning environments (Bond Bedenlier, 2019). In Asia, particularly in Indonesia, the integration of digital tools into language teaching introduces additional complexity, as teachers often face difficulties in utilizing technology to cater to the diverse needs of learners. While digital resources like language learning apps, e-books, and multimedia materials have the potential to enhanced language acquisition, many teachers lack the necessary training and support to used these tools effectively in their classrooms (Alanoglu,et.al., 2022). In the Philippine setting, particularly in Masbate, Bicol Region, the transition from traditional to digital teaching methods has posed striking challenges for English language teachers, particularly in rural and underfunded areas. While technology has the potential to enhanced teaching, many teachers struggle to balance the integration of ICT with the need for contextualized, learner-centered instruction for learners. The demand for new technical skills, alongside the necessity to adapt pedagogical strategies, places a strain on teachers who are already burdened with heavy workloads and insufficient resources (Banares, 2020). Also in some public rural schools in Luzon, teachers face challenges not only in acquiring new digital tools but also in mastering their use in the classroom. Professional development opportunities remain limited, particularly in more remote areas, where teachers often have little access to training programs or workshops focused on ICT integration. This gap in professional learning heightens the difficulty of applying technology effectively to meet the diverse needs of learners, leaving teachers unable to fully capitalize on the potential benefits of digital tools for language acquisition (Figuroa, 2020). In Iloilo City, public schools face significant challenges due to the lack of institutional support and insufficient technological infrastructure, which hinder the effective used of ICT in education. Despite increasing recognition of the importance of technology in enhancing teaching and learning, many schools in this region still struggle with limited access to reliable internet and digital devices. This gap in resources leaves teachers unable to fully leverage the potential of ICT-based instruction, making it difficult to deliver quality education that meets the demands of modern digital learning (Almerich et al., 2022). Locally, in Panabo City, English teachers face several challenges in integrating digital technology into their teaching practices, particularly in creating safe learning environments while dealing with technological constraints. Insufficient digital tools for learning were often the encountered obstacles of teachers, as well as the limited access to ICT resources, limited infrastructure, and varying levels of digital literacy gaps among educators and learners. Teachers highlighted the critical role of institutional supported in overcoming these barriers and ensuring successful technology adoption. Their lived experiences emphasized the need for continuous training, resources, and guidance to effectively integrate digital tools into the teaching and learning process (Requillo Bauyot, 2024). From the literatures accessed by the researcher, it had been eminent that some of the studies previously conducted, just like the study conducted by Dillon et al., (2019) and in the study conducted by Banares (2020) and Figuroa (2020). These mentioned studies were quantitative in nature while the proposed study will be qualita-

tive specifically, narrative approach to explore English teachers’ instructional technology experiences of public junior high school teachers. The researcher recognized the urgency to conduct this study in order to delve deeper into the instructional experiences of public junior high school teachers regarding digital technology, using a narrative approach. This research aims to address the gap in existing literature, particularly within the context of the Panabo City Division.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The primary purpose of this narrative study is to explore and highlighted the instructional technology experiences of teachers, focusing on how they integrate and navigate digital tools in their teaching practices. By examining these experiences, the study aims to provide insights that can inform the development of effective strategies and supported for teachers in enhancing their technology-driven instruction. Conducting a narrative study on teachers’ experiences with instructional technology is significant as it offers a deeper understanding of the challenges and successes teachers face in integrating digital tools into their classrooms. This insight can inform policies, professional development programs, and strategies that may empower educators to effectively harness technology to enhance teaching and learning outcomes, drawn from the findings of the study that will be conducted in Panabo Central District, Panabo City Division.

1.2. Research Questions—This study will be conducted to delve on the experiences of teachers on their digital journey towards instructional technology delivery. The direction of this study will be set by the following specific research questions:

- (1) What experiences have shaped your integration of instructional technology in teaching English?
- (2) What specific coping strategies were used?
- (3) What values can be drawn from the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—English Teachers This study offers a deeper understanding of the opportunities and challenges in using instructional technology, enabling them to refine their digital teaching strategies and improved classroom effectiveness. It will also provide practical examples and insights that can inspired and guide their own technology integration efforts.

1.4. Significant of the Study—This study will be beneficial to the learners, English teachers, principals, Department of Education and future researchers.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study is anchored on the Distributed Cognitive Theory (Hutchin, 2000). The theory emphasized that knowledge is not purely individual but dependent on the social and physical environment in analyzing educational technologies and human-computer interaction. In addition, this theory describes how information processing is dispersed across people and their workplace, their technologies, and their social organizations and how information processing evolves. The theory highlighted that knowledge is not solely an individual cognitive process but is influenced by the social and physical environment, particularly in the context of technology integration. It also emphasized how information process-

ing is distributed across individuals, their tools, and the organizational structures they engaged with, evolving as interactions unfold. In the context of this study, the theory supports the exploration of English teachers' experiences with instructional technology as shaped by their social settings, technological tools, and institutional support, offering insights into how these elements collectively influence the effectiveness of digital tools in education. Also, the study is supported by Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989). TAM theory explores how individuals come to accept and effectively use new technologies based on their perceptions and behavioral responses. In the context of instructional technology, teachers' willingness to adopt digital tools is influenced by factors such as perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness, which were core components of TAM. It supported the idea that teachers were more likely to integrate technology into their classrooms if they believe it will enhance teaching efficiency and improved student engagement. Additionally, external factors such as institutional support, training, and cultural attitudes toward technology can significantly impact teachers' decisions on when and how to incorporate digital tools into their teaching practices. Another theory that supported the study is the Technological

Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) model (Mishra and Koehler, 2006). This theory highlighted the interplay between three primary forms of knowledge: content knowledge (CK), pedagogical knowledge (PK), and technological knowledge (TK). In the context of English teaching, TPACK emphasized the need for teachers to integrate technology effectively into their instructional strategies, ensuring that it aligned with both their content expertise and pedagogical approaches. TPACK supported the exploration of how English teachers navigate the integration of digital tools in their classrooms by considering how technology intersects with content and teaching methods. According to TPACK, successful technology integration occurs when teachers were not only proficient in using technology but also understand how it enhanced content delivery and teaching strategies. This model is particularly relevant for understanding the challenges and strategies English teachers adopt when incorporating instructional technologies into their practices. As presented in the conceptual framework labeled as Figure 1, there were two interconnected variables. These variables were the experiences that shaped the integration of instructional technology in teaching English, specific coping strategies, and values drawn from the study.

2. Methodology

This chapter of the study presented the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study and the ethical consideration. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitates the consequent design and implementation as elaborated in this chapter

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—I used a phenomenological research design that was exploratory in nature, drawing on facets of information derived from fluid, subjective experiences and the perspectives of participants. This design proved most suitable for the exploratory nature of the study. It began with assump-

tions and utilized an interpretive framework that aligned with the research problems, specifically in addressing the perceptions of individuals or groups as transcribed into a human social problem. The underlying philosophical assumptions of the research were identified. To advance the study, the researcher employed an emerging phe-

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

nomenological inquiry, collected data in a natural setting sensitive to the people and places involved, and used both inductive and deductive approaches to establish patterns and themes. The final written report or presentation included participants' experiences and offered a reflexive, complex description and interpretation of the problem, contributing to the existing literature or advocating for change. The underlying philosophical assumptions that validated the research were identified: ontology, epistemology, axiology, and rhetoric (Creswell, 2020). As a researcher involved in this investigation, I consistently recognized and was shaped by a broad range of perspectives regarding the essence of reality, the means by which knowledge was acquired, the role of values in the research process, and the approaches used throughout the inquiry

Ontology

I examined the nature of reality and existence by utilizing qualitative research to explore what defined reality, how it could be understood, and the diverse realities that participants might share. This approach acknowledged multiple realities that could be explored and constructed through human interactions and meaningful actions, as reflected in the participants' actual

words. Their stories, experiences, and responses were carefully documented and analyzed in relation to the nature of reality. Given the complexity of the environment in which nursing research occurred, qualitative researchers, including myself, had to confront this intricacy. This perspective assumed the existence of a reality independent of the researcher that could be understood. I relied on the participants' voices and interpretations, captured their direct quotes, and identified themes representing their viewpoints, thereby providing insights into varying perspectives. The responses were systematically coded and analyzed to uncover both commonalities and differences. I ensured the accuracy and reliability of the results by meticulously coding the responses, preserving their authenticity, and minimizing personal bias throughout the research process.

Epistemological Assumptions

At the heart of the inquiry lay the question of what defined knowledge. In contrast to a positivist paradigm, which viewed knowledge as objective and measurable through strict scientific methods, this study gathered insights through empathetic understanding of participants' lived social realities. The objective

was to describe individuals' subjective experiences, perceptions, and interpretations. I, as a qualitative researcher, endeavored to connect deeply with the participants. Hence, subjective data was collected based on their personal viewpoints, showing that knowledge was constructed through individual lived experiences. I reflected on and articulated my epistemological stance—how I understood knowledge, research, science, and broader worldviews. Identifying whether I aligned with positivism, structural realism, or post-positivism was crucial in shaping these perspectives. In qualitative research, it was important to position myself within one or more philosophical frameworks. This foundation informed my research questions, guided my methods, and influenced how I interpreted and applied data. Ultimately, this philosophical foundation shaped my research design and its progression, grounded in theoretical principles (Turner, 2020). According to Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2013), the researcher reduced the distance between themselves and the participants. I ensured a close interaction with the participants, spending time in the field and becoming an “insider.” I gained direct information that shed light on the knowledge surrounding the inquiry, particularly about schools' experiences and coping strategies in implementing the program during the new normal. These epistemological assumptions, which emphasized subjective evidence, were particularly important in data collection conducted through fieldwork and in understanding contextual aspects such as location accessibility.

Ontological Assumptions

This component of the research pertained to how the issue related to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2020), reality was seen as subjective and multiple by participants in the study. Ontologically, qualitative researchers recognized that reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research context. Therefore, multiple realities existed: those of the

researcher, the individuals being studied, and the readers or audiences interpreting the findings. This study elaborated on the realities of implementing online distance learning during the pandemic when face-to-face classes were suspended. I believed that individuals perceived these realities in diverse ways, shaped by their personal experiences. I drew on the voices and interpretations of participants, using detailed quotations and themes to express their perspectives. Their responses were categorized and analyzed to identify both similarities and differences. I ensured the responses were meticulously processed to uphold the consistency and reliability of the findings, maintaining the integrity of the data and minimizing personal biases throughout the research.

Axiological Assumptions

I acknowledged my biases as a researcher and explicitly reported them, recognizing that they helped assess whether the observed environment accurately reflected participants' behaviors. Axiological assumptions explored how values and biases shaped the narrative and interpretation of phenomena. These assumptions considered not only the participants' goals, values, mission statements, beliefs, and opinions but also my interpretations as a researcher. Axiological research recognized that both participants' behaviors and researchers' observations were affected by personal biases (Kulinska, 2016). In this study, axiological assumptions were used to address ethically significant experiences. My personal values, intuition, and biases played a pivotal role in shaping the research process and interpretation of findings. These philosophical premises, while grounded in practicality, influenced the theoretical foundations that supported the research methodology. I recognized that my values were inherent in data interpretation, shaping both methodology and outcomes. Qualitative researchers emphasized the importance of recognizing and documenting the belief systems and philosoph-

ical frameworks guiding their work. To enhance the rhetorical dimension, I adopted a personal, conversational, and accessible tone throughout the research. Axiology suggested that researchers openly acknowledge the values shaping the narrative and include their own interpretations alongside those of the participants. I respected the integrity and worth of the information gathered. I was mindful of the value-laden nature of the data, ensuring that participants' responses were authentically interpreted with sensitivity to their context and perspectives.

Rhetorical

In qualitative research, the core rhetorical assumption held that the researcher was not an omniscient truth-seeker, but rather a storyteller who conveyed reality through participants' perspectives. The rhetoric of research addressed the use of language to convey findings effectively while remaining cautious of potential manipulation through insincere or deceptive lan-

guage. I aimed to uncover truth as perceived by my participants, presenting their experiences as essential insights. The goal was to portray a reality shaped by their interpretations, acknowledging the subjective nature of knowledge. I aligned with the postmodern philosophy articulated by Afzal-os-Sadat Hossieni (2011), which emphasized that the purpose of education extended beyond teaching critical thinking to fostering knowledge creation, identity formation, and self-empowerment. In postmodern education, teachers encouraged learners to explore new ideas and engaged in creative dialogue. This approach enabled them to appreciate differing perspectives, embrace criticism constructively, and think critically. It also emphasized cooperative learning, independent thought, and dialectical discourse, integrating postmodern and creative elements into the educational process.

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—This study, which focused on junior high school English teachers' instructional technology delivery in Panabo Central District, Panabo City Division, collected data through In-Depth Interviews (IDI), Focus Group Discussions (FGD), and responses directly from participants. My efforts in understanding the lived experiences of junior high school teachers in delivering instruction through technology served as the foundation for this narrative-qualitative research. This method was useful in uncovering meanings and motivations behind cultural symbols, personal experiences, and perspectives (Creswell, 2020). Conducting this narrative research on instructional technology delivery in English was essential to understanding how teachers navigated the integration of digital tools into their classrooms. This approach provided a platform for educators to share their personal stories, revealing the im-

pact of technology on their teaching practices, student engagement, and curriculum delivery. Through these narratives, the study offered insights into the dynamics of instructional technology, which could inform strategies for enhancing English language teaching. These findings supported the development of more effective, innovative teaching methods suitable for 21st-century learning demands. The study's relevance extended to guiding policymakers, school leaders, and educators in shaping educational practices. Teachers' stories highlighted the gaps in training, resources, and supported necessary for effective technology integration. Furthermore, the research addressed broader issues of digital literacy in English education, stressing its importance in preparing learners for a globally connected world. Ultimately, the research informed educational reform and advocated for empowering teachers as agents of change in technology-enhanced learning environments.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This research used a narrative approach to understand and interpret individuals' lived experiences by collecting and analyzing their stories in rich detail (Clandinin Connelly, 2000). This qualitative method highlighted the value of personal accounts in comprehending how people made sense of their experiences within particular social, cultural, and educational contexts. By examining these narratives, I uncovered deeper insights into the processes, challenges, and successes encountered by participants. The method proved especially valuable in the educational field, where understanding teacher and learner experiences was central to grasp-

2.4. *Research Participants*—Qualitative analyses typically required fewer participants compared to quantitative approaches. The sample size in qualitative studies was sufficient to capture the range of perceptions necessary to reach saturation. Saturation was reached when adding more participants no longer yielded new insights or information. According to Glaser and Strauss (1967), the concept of saturation was essential for determining an appropriate sample size in qualitative research, ensuring that all relevant perspectives were captured and analyzed. Purposive sampling was employed in identifying participants for this study. Through purposive sampling, a non-probability sample was selected based on characteristics of a population and the objective of the study. Purposively, the researcher selected 10 junior high school teachers from a public school in Panabo

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—The ethical considerations were significant in the design of this research study. The researcher considered several ethical issues about the research participants in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations were specified as one of the most important

ing teaching and learning dynamics. The narrative research aimed to give voice to individuals, allowing them to articulate their unique experiences and viewpoints in their own words (Riessman, 2008). Through this method, I constructed a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon by placing personal stories within wider social and educational frameworks. Narrative research facilitated the identification of recurring themes, patterns, and meanings that could inform policy, enhance practice, or guide further inquiry. Ultimately, the method contributed to a more nuanced and meaningful understanding of human experiences, especially in the ever-evolving landscape of education.

Central District, Division of Panabo City six participants for the in-depth interview, and four participants for the focus group discussion with a total of ten secondary school teachers invited as participants. Inclusion criteria were as follows: currently a permanent English teacher in a public junior high school in Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City, and teaching English subject for five years. The results were used to identify the emerging themes and patterns of responses based on their lived experiences. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2020). It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic.

parts of the research. The researcher adhered to promoting the aims of the research by imparting authentic knowledge, truth, and prevention of error. Social Value This study emphasized the implication of exploring the instructional technology experiences of junior high school

English teachers. By focusing on their journey, the research shed light on the practical challenges and opportunities that technology brought to education, offering insights into how teaching and learning could be enhanced. The findings served as a valuable resource for education policymakers and administrators, encouraging the development of innovative programs and strategies that improved the use of technology in classrooms. These initiatives fostered a more supportive environment where both educators and learners thrived, enhancing the overall quality of education. By highlighting the contribution of instructional technology, the study contributed to the broader goal of building an education system that prepared students for future challenges. Teachers equipped with effective tools and strategies delivered more engaging and impactful lessons, inspiring learners to embrace curiosity and lifelong learning. The societal implications of this research extended to creating healthier educational ecosystems that benefited not only educators and students but also families and communities. Ultimately, the study advocated for informed decision-making in educational practices and policies, ensuring a well-rounded and future-ready society. Informed Consent Participants were invited to join the research with the assurance that their involvement remained entirely voluntary and based on a clear understanding of the provided information. The recruitment and selection process was outlined in detail within the appendices of the study. Establishing trust and securing the support of participants was vital to conducting an ethical and informed academic inquiry. Following Creswell's (2020) principles, this phenomenological research emphasized transparency and respect for participants' perspectives to ensure credibility and integrity throughout the study. All of the participants were provided with an informed consent form. Each participant signed a personal acknowledgment, granting consent and indicating their will-

ingness to participate in the study. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research objectives, provide the researcher's contact information, explain the study's intent, request voluntary participation, and outline the type of information participants were expected to share. Participants were required to sign and return the consent form to the researcher prior to engaging in any aspect of the study. Vulnerability of Research Participants The participants of this study were the junior high school English teachers who could answer the research instrument as they were all of legal age. Thus, the researcher assured them that he or she could easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there were clarifications or questions about the study. Risks, Benefits and Safety

The recruitment of respondents was conducted without any coercion, undue influence, or incentives. Participants were provided with contact information for the chair of the panel or other panel members should they have had any questions or concerns about the study. Additionally, if any respondent felt discomfort or inconvenience while answering questions, they were not pressured to continue their participation. The researcher ensured that all respondents were safe during the interview process. The interview took place in a secure setting and was scheduled at a time that was convenient for the participants. The study adhered to the Treaty Principle of Protection, ensuring respect for participants' privacy, confidentiality, and minimizing any potential risks. This was achieved by assigning pseudonyms to the respondents to protect their identities. Any inherent risks were minimized through careful steps to ensure confidentiality and participant safety. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information

This study complied with the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the participants' identities were protected and that the data could not be traced back to them. Strict measures

were taken to maintained the anonymity of the data sources, ensuring that any printed materials resulting from the study kept the identities of participants confidential. Furthermore, the study was conducted with full consideration of potential conflicts of interest, ensuring transparency and fairness in the research process. Any form of misleading information, as well as biased representation of the primary data findings, was avoided to maintain the integrity of the study. Justice The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their own responsibilities during the data collection process. They were briefed on the importance of providing honest responses to the survey questions and were encouraged to communicate openly and truthfully throughout the research. Additionally, participants were made aware that they would be the first to benefit from the findings of the study. This transparency helped ensure that all participants understood their involvement and the impact of the research results. Transparency The results of the study were made accessible to the respondents and heads of the participating schools, as the information was stored on CDs or other storage devices, which they could request from the researcher. By reviewing the findings, junior high school teachers gained insight into the importance of the study and how it could positively influence their well-being. Additionally, each participant was informed that they had the right to withdraw their information at any time before the completion of data collection, and they had the opportunity to review their individual transcripts after the interviews. This allowed participants to correct or remove any details they felt might identify them. The researcher retained the right to use pseudonyms and alter names or non-significant dates in order to protect participants' identities in all future data analysis and reporting. This measure ensured confidentiality and safeguarded the privacy of the individuals involved. Qualification of the Researcher The researcher ensured that

she possessed the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher completed the academic requirements, passed the comprehensive examination prior to thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the masteral degree, and was qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study reached its completion.

Adequacy of Facilities

The researcher worked diligently to ensure that the study was completed within the specified time-frame and that all necessary resources were available. The technical committee played a crucial role in enhancing the study by providing valuable suggestions and recommendations for improvement. Additionally, the researcher secured sufficient funding to continue and complete the research process. As a result, the study was completed as planned, within the target time-frame. Community Involvement The researcher demonstrated respect for the local traditions, culture, and perspectives of the respondents throughout the study. Additionally, the study ensured complete transparency, with no deception used at any stage, including in the recruitment of participants or the methods of data collection. The researcher also expressed sincere appreciation for the full and willing participation of the interviewees in the research process. This approach fostered trust and respect throughout the duration of the study.

Plagiarism and Fabrication as the Researcher The researcher acknowledged prior works by appropriately citing the original authors and rephrasing their ideas in her own words. The researcher also used direct quotations when referencing text taken from other sources. Furthermore, the researcher ensured that the manuscript was crafted with integrity, avoiding any intentional misrepresentation or fabrication of data, and refrained from presenting conclusions that were not supported by the actual findings. The focus was on maintaining

accuracy and honesty throughout the study's development.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher conducted interviews with the participants and guided them throughout the process. The researcher ensured that all interpretations of responses were grounded in existing literature and related studies. To avoid bias, the researcher refrained from imposing personal opinions, feelings, or assumptions on the data.

*2.7. Data Collection—*The data collection process was structured and ethical, beginning with the submission of a revised research proposal to the Ethics approval, followed by deans endorsement, informed consent from participants, in-depth interviews, and thematic content analysis to identify patterns and emerging themes, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the participants' experiences. Ethics Approval. The revised research proposal was submitted to the ethics committee. All recommendations and suggestions provided by the committee were incorporated to ensure that the study adhered to ethical standards. Upon final review, the committee issued an ethics clearance certificate to signify approval.

Dean's Endorsement. A formal endorsement letter was requested from the Dean of the Graduate School to confirmed institutional support and that ethical standards were met. Approval from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS). After obtaining the endorsement from the Dean, a formal request to conduct the study was submitted to the SDS, including Chapters 1 and 2 and the research instruments. Approval from the SDS was granted to proceed

2.8. Data Analysis—

Expert in Qualitative Method. The researcher applied qualitative methods with precision by seeking advice from the research adviser and other professionals. This enabled the researcher to competently design and conduct interviews, perform field observations, select relevant artifacts and journals, and execute Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis effectively.

with the study. Cluster Supervisor School Head Approval. Following the SDS's approval, formal permissions were obtained from the Cluster Supervisor and respective school heads of each identified junior high school within the chosen division. Informed Consent. Informed consent letters were distributed to participants and their guardians. Participants were briefed on the nature of the study, and only those who voluntarily agreed participated in the interviews.

vConducting Interviews. The researcher conducted in-depth interviews using a semi-structured interview guide. Notes were taken, conversations were recorded, and the researcher listened actively to ensured responses were accurately captured.

Transcription Translation. The responses were transcribed verbatim from the audio recordings. Transcripts in Filipino or other local dialects were translated into English to ensure consistency and comprehensibility. Thematic Content Analysis. The responses were analyzed by identifying codes, patterns, and emerging themes. To validate the accuracy of the data, a follow-up focus group discussion (FGD) was conducted, providing participants an opportunity to resonated the interpretations.

Thematic analysis was used as the primary approach for analyzing the data. The researcher collected and categorized responses into emerging themes using Thematic Content Analysis and Environmental Triangulation. The process allowed the researcher to explore the lived experiences of junior high school English teachers in relation to the instructional technologies they used. Themes were extracted and connected to existing literature. Creswell’s Model was followed, emphasizing data collection, transcription, interpretation, and meaningful presentation of results. The study employed Braun Clarke’s (2022) Reflexive Thematic Analysis to analyze data: Familiarization with the Data. The researcher reviewed the raw data by reading and re-reading the transcribed responses to

become deeply immersed in the content. Generating Initial Codes. Relevant features and meanings from the responses were systematically coded. Constructing Themes. Initial codes were clustered into meaningful themes based on related ideas or shared meanings. Reviewing Themes. The identified themes were refined and reviewed to ensure they accurately represented the responses and captured the essence of the data. Defining and Naming Themes. Themes were named and defined in alignment with the research questions, using actual excerpts from the participants. Writing Up. A final report was written, capturing the participants’ lived experiences and reflecting the themes and insights derived from the data.

2.9. Framework of Analysis—

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Trustworthiness was established by addressing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In a qualitative study, trustworthiness was essential because the results and findings of the research depended on how the process was conducted by the researcher. The trustworthiness of a research study was critical in evaluating its value. Given the nature of qualitative research, honesty in all data and details was required. Trustworthiness made the researcher’s study worthy of being read, shared, and taken pride in.

Credibility

Credibility referred to how confident the qualitative researcher was in the truth of the study’s findings. In this study, the researcher believed that honesty in every action was essential to achieving meaningful success. The researcher had no derogatory records or administrative issues that could have undermined her integrity. Lincoln and Guba (2000) stated that

credibility referred to the idea of internal consistency, where the main concern was “how we ensure rigor in the research process and how we communicate to others that we have done so.” Transferability Transferability referred to how the qualitative researcher demonstrated that the research study’s findings were applicable to other contexts. In this case, “other contexts” meant similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. The researcher had already studied the effects brought about by the parents’ reading intervention on learners’ literacy. With this, the researcher was interested in knowing the secondary teachers’ perspectives. Gasson (2004) emphasized transferability as the extent to which the reader was able to generalize the study based on their own context and addressed the core issue of “how far a researcher may make claims for a general application of the theory.” Confirmability Confirmability referred to the degree of neutrality in the research study’s findings. In other words, this

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

meant that the findings were based on participants' responses and not on any potential bias or personal motivations of the researcher. This involved ensuring that researcher bias did not skew the interpretation of the participants' statements to fit a certain narrative. The information using the audit trail in this situation was thoughtfully recorded by the researcher, highlighting every step of data analysis made to provide a rationale for the decisions taken. This helped establish that the research study's findings accurately portrayed participants' responses. Gasson (2004) stated that confirmability was based on the acknowledgement that research was never fully objective.

Dependability

Dependability referred to the extent to which the study could be repeated by other re-

searchers and yield consistent findings. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate the study, they should have had enough information from the research report to do so and obtain similar results. A qualitative researcher used an inquiry audit to establish dependability, which required an outside person to review and examine the research process and data analysis to ensure that the findings were consistent and could be repeated. In this component, the use of a database was very important in backing up collected information and noting changes for all types of research studies. All the data collected was properly kept for future reference. Gasson (2004) stated that dependability dealt with the core issue that "the way in which a study is conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques."

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the study's results, analyzing participants' narratives and themes. It integrates findings with relevant literature, highlighting both similarities and differences. The aim is to answer research questions and provide meaningful interpretations based on participants' voices.

3.1. Experiences that shaped the Integration of Instructional Technology in teaching English—The integration of instructional technology in teaching English among the participants was largely shaped by the sudden transition to remote learning brought about by the pandemic. Many initially encountered challenges in navigating unfamiliar digital platforms, but through continuous exposure, collaboration, and professional development, they gradually adapted. Over time, the use of various technological tools allowed them to design more engaging and interactive lessons that catered to diverse learner needs. These collective experiences highlighted how technology could transform traditional in-

struction into a more dynamic, student-centered, and inclusive learning environment. The participants observed that learners' positive responses and increased participation encouraged them to further explore and refine their teaching strategies. Many noted that the integration of multimedia elements and interactive digital activities contributed to improved comprehension and engagement in language learning. As a result, their instructional roles gradually shifted from traditional knowledge delivery to facilitation of more dynamic and blended learning environments. This transformation emerged as they collectively overcame initial technological challenges and embraced a more student-centered approach to teaching English.

3.1.1. Professional Development and Mentorship—

The integration of instructional technology in English teaching was heavily influenced by teachers' exposure to professional development activities such as workshops, trainings, and mentorship programs. These formal learning experiences provided teachers with the foundational knowledge, practical tools, and pedagogical strategies necessary for effective technology integration. Mentorship in particular played a pivotal role in guiding novice educators through real-life applications of instructional technology. Learning alongside experienced mentors helped them bridge theory with practice, making the process of adopting technology in classrooms more efficient and purposeful. The study findings aligned with the study of Alanoglu et al., (2022), who emphasized the importance of systematic teacher training in ICT integration. Their research suggested that teachers were more effective in digital classrooms when they receive ongoing, structured training tailored to their instructional context. This is mirrored in the current study, where participants reported that workshops and seminars significantly enhanced their capacity to use technology effectively. The findings supported the need for training programs that blended theoretical knowledge with practical application to support classroom integration. The findings also supported the study of Haleem et al. (2022), who found that participation in digital literacy programs increases teachers' self-efficacy and their willingness to adopt new technologies. In this study, participants demonstrated higher confi-

3.1.2. Classroom Practice and Student Engagement—Teachers' actual classroom experiences deeply shaped how they integrated technology in English instruction. They found that tools such as PowerPoint, AI applications, and gamified activities significantly increased student participation and interest. These experiences validated technology as a means to deliver content in a more dynamic and relatable way.

dence and adaptability after engaging in webinars and peer-led training sessions. Teachers who had undergone digital upskilling reported improved competence in navigating digital tools and managing tech-enhanced classrooms. This reinforced the role of professional development in building both skills and a positive attitude toward ICT use. Similarly, the study corroborates the findings of Behera and Deb (2020), who highlighted that continuous professional development enables educators to integrate technology more meaningfully into pedagogy. Teachers in this study confirmed that repeated exposure to ICT through training allowed them to modify their instructional strategies effectively. They were able to incorporate multimedia and interactive tools in ways that aligned with lesson objectives. This reflects how sustained learning opportunities contribute to long-term improvement in digital instruction practices. Finally, the study findings supported the observations of Figueroa (2020), who pointed out that limited access to training in rural schools hampers effective technology use. Participants in this study from less resourced areas shared similar sentiments, noting that initial struggles with digital tools were due to lack of exposure and institutional support. Mentorship programs played a key role in bridging this gap by offering individualized guidance. These findings highlighted the need for equitable access to professional development, especially in underserved teaching contexts.

Educators noticed that interactive instructional technology made student-centered approaches more effective. In response, they modified their teaching styles to better support learner engagement. They also redesigned their materials to take full advantage of tech-driven strategies that enhanced learning. The study findings supported the study of Lembani et al. (2020), who underscored the effectiveness of gamified

and interactive tools in enhancing student motivation and engagement. Participants in this study similarly reported that digital games and interactive platforms increased learner participation in English classes. The use of tools like Bamboozle and animated presentations helped capture student attention and sustain interest. These results confirmed that gamification can significantly improve classroom dynamics and learning outcomes. The findings also aligned with the research of Behera and Deb (2020), who emphasized that digital tools strengthen feedback mechanisms and student engagement. Teachers in the current study shared how multimedia tools allowed them to provide real-time responses and adjust lessons to student needs. These strategies supported formative assessment and reinforced learning through personalized instruction. The evidence highlighted how digital integration fosters a more responsive and student-centered learning environment. In addition, the study findings corroborate the con-

3.1.3. Adaptation to Institutional Resources and Environment—Teachers' experiences with instructional technology were also shaped by the available infrastructure and support within their respective schools. Access to digital tools such as smart TVs, projectors, laptops, and school-provided platforms largely influenced how technology was utilized in the classroom. Instead of focusing solely on ideal resources, teachers demonstrated practical adaptability by aligning their instructional design with what either enable or limit technology integration in educational settings. The findings of this study aligned with the study of Bond and Bedenlier (2019), who discussed the impact of the digital divide on educators' capacity to integrate ICT effectively. They emphasized that inadequate infrastructure and limited access to devices can hinder meaningful use of technology in classrooms. Similarly, teachers in Panabo reported facing constraints such as insuff-

cient internet connectivity and outdated hardware. Despite these limitations, they adapted by utilizing what was available, showcasing resilience and creativity in instructional delivery. The study also supported the findings of Requillo and Bauyot (2024), who noted that successful ICT adoption depends heavily on the availability of digital tools and institutional support. Teachers in the current study highlighted the role of school provisions such as laptops, smart TVs, and projectors in facilitating digital instruction. Moreover, mentorship and administrative encouragement played a crucial role in helping teachers overcome technological challenges. These experiences validated the need for systemic support structures to sustain digital transformation in education. Similarly, the results aligned with Almerich et al. (2022), who emphasized that institutional infrastructure is a critical factor in effective ICT implementation in public schools. Participants indicated that

Participants indicated that digital resources promoted creativity and expand access to educational content. Participants in this study noted that technology enabled them to design more varied and inclusive instructional materials. These tools helped cater to different learning styles, particularly through audio-visual formats. As a result, students became more engaged and independent in their learning processes. Lastly, the results were in agreement with the study of Tan et al. (2019), who argued that technology is most effective when aligned with specific learning objectives. Teachers in this study demonstrated purposeful integration of digital tools into lesson plans, ensuring that activities supported targeted language competencies. Their experience confirmed that clear pedagogical planning is essential in maximizing the educational impact of ICT. This alignment between tools and goals contributed to improved language acquisition and classroom performance.

Fig. 3. Experiences that Shaped the Integration of Instructional Technology in teaching English

the degree of their technology used was directly related to the quality and quantity of resources provided by the school. Those with better access were able to design more engaging and interactive lessons, while others faced limitations in content delivery. This suggested that equitable resource distribution is essential to ensure all learners benefit from digital education. Moreover, the findings resonated with the study of Feng (2020), who highlighted how digital tools can improved classroom management and

instruction when appropriately aligned with resource availability. Teachers in this study shared how they used technology not only for lesson delivery but also for monitoring and motivating student behavior. Interactive platforms were employed to streamline routines and create a more structured learning environment. These outcomes demonstrated how digital tools, when used within infrastructural limits, can enhanced both teaching efficiency and learner engagement

3.2. Specific Coping Strategies Used in teaching English—To cope with the demands of integrating instructional technology, I adopted a mindset of continuous learning and flexibility. I enrolled in webinars, joined professional learning communities, and sought mentorship from more tech-savvy colleagues. These strategies not only improved my technical skills but also gave me emotional support during overwhelm-

ing transitions. I also practiced self-paced learning, setting achievable goals to avoid burnout while managing both teaching responsibilities and personal growth. Moreover, I involved learners in the process by encouraging feedback on the tools and approaches I used. This collaborative dynamic helped reduce pressure, as I no longer carried the burden of innovation alone. I learned to celebrate small wins, such as a suc-

successful virtual activity or increased student participation, which fueled my motivation. These

coping mechanisms helped me stay grounded, resilient, and open to change.

3.2.1. Instructional Flexibility and Backup Planning—Teachers acknowledged that technology is not always reliable, so having contingency plans was vital. They developed the habit of preparing hard copies, printable materials, or offline activities in case of unexpected disruptions like power outages or software failures. This strategic foresight ensured teaching and learning continued without compromising class objectives. Moreover, instructional flexibility allowed educators to adapt their lessons according to classroom conditions and technological limitations. Whether through adjusting to available equipment or modifying lesson delivery on the fly, this theme highlighted teachers' resilience and preparedness in navigating tech-related challenges. The findings of this study were consistent with the work of Dillon et al. (2019), who observed that teachers often implement rotation schedules, distribute hard copies, and use preloaded materials to compensate for limited access to technology. Participants in the current study adopted similar approaches, especially in response to power interruptions or unstable internet connections. These practical solutions enabled them to sustain instructional delivery despite infrastructural barriers. Such coping mechanisms reflect the ingenuity required when resources are inadequate. The study also supported the conclusions of Tam (2020), who emphasized the importance of hav-

ing contingency plans to ensure lesson continuity during digital disruptions. Teachers in this research frequently prepared backup activities, such as printed worksheets and offline tasks, in case of technical failures. These preparations helped maintain learning momentum even under unpredictable circumstances. Tam's insights highlighted the value of foresight and strategic planning in tech-integrated teaching. Similarly, the study findings aligned with Huang et al. (2020), who stressed that teachers often rely on self-initiated efforts like peer collaboration and internet-based troubleshooting when formal technical support is unavailable. In the current study, teachers described turning to colleagues and online forums for immediate solutions to tech-related issues. This peer-based support system proved essential in building digital confidence and ensuring continuity in instruction. These experiences reflect a culture of shared learning and resilience. Lastly, the study findings reinforce those of Zheng et al. (2022), who reported that educators frequently engage in self-paced learning to overcome gaps in formal training. Teachers in this study pursued online tutorials, webinars, and independent study to enhance their digital competence. This proactive approach allowed them to keep up with evolving educational technologies despite minimal institutional guidance. Their commitment to self-improvement illustrated how personal initiative can mitigate systemic limitations.

3.2.2. Classroom Management and Student-Centered Approaches—Participants emphasized that coping strategies extended beyond technology and into classroom dynamics. Managing student behavior, addressing diverse learning needs, and fostering collaborative learning

environments were critical. Establishing clear expectations and promoting peer-assisted learning were central to creating effective classroom management systems. These strategies not only reduced teacher stress but also empowered students to become active participants in their own

learning. Through differentiated activities and peer support, teachers created adaptive spaces that encouraged participation from learners of all levels. The results of this study affirmed the conclusions of Kormos (2022), who emphasized that teachers' beliefs, attitudes, and adaptability significantly shape how they manage classrooms and implement digital tools. In this study, teachers demonstrated flexibility by employing peer-assisted learning and designing differentiated tasks to meet varied student needs. Their willingness to adjust instructional strategies reflects how mindset and openness to innovation affect classroom dynamics. This alignment showed that internal dispositions are as important as external tools in successful ICT integration. The findings were also in agreement with Laudari and Maher (2019), who pointed out that many educators struggle to translate their theoretical understanding of technology into effective classroom practice. Participants in this study echoed this sentiment, explaining how they initially faced difficulties but gradually developed practical approaches through experience and mentorship. They bridged the theory-practice gap by learning through doing and observing peers. This supported the need for experiential learning in ICT training programs.

In addition, the study supported the observations of Banares (2020), who found that teachers must simultaneously adjust their teaching strategies and classroom management styles when adopting instructional technology. Participants described how the shift to digital methods required them to rethink not just lesson delivery but also how they engage and organize their students. These adaptations were necessary to maintain classroom order and ensure learning continuity. The evidence underscores that technology integration affects both instructional and behavioral dimensions of teaching. Finally, the findings aligned with Requillo and Bauyot (2024), who emphasized the role of collaboration and teacher autonomy in overcoming technological barriers. In this study, participants frequently sought support from colleagues and shared best practices to improve their digital instruction. This culture of collaboration empowered them to respond effectively to challenges in diverse learning environments. Their actions demonstrated how teacher agency and peer networks contribute to successful technology integration.

3.2.3. Use of Multimedia and Gamification—Gamified learning and multimedia tools were frequently cited as effective coping mechanisms by English teachers. These strategies not only addressed student boredom but also made abstract concepts more accessible through visual, auditory, and interactive elements. Tools like Bamboozle, YouTube videos, and storytelling platforms served both pedagogical and motivational purposes. Teachers found that using games, videos, and dynamic media could engage students with varied learning styles, helping them connect emotionally and intellectually with lesson content. These approaches also created a more relaxed and enjoyable learn-

ing atmosphere, which eased the pressure on both students and educators. The study's findings aligned with the study of Layng (2023), who stressed the value of incorporating various multimedia tools to design dynamic and engaging classroom experiences. Teachers in this study reported frequent use of platforms such as YouTube, digital storytelling, and educational games to enhance lesson delivery. These tools were selected to match students' interests and preferred learning styles, making lessons more relatable and effective. Layng's emphasis on personalization and media diversity is directly reflected in the strategies adopted by the participant. The findings also supported

Fig. 4. Specific Coping Strategies Used in Teaching English

the conclusions of Lembani et al. (2020), who advocated for the use of gamified learning apps to improved student comprehension and retention. Teachers in the study specifically mentioned using interactive tools like Bamboozle, which created a fun and engaging learning environment. These applications helped reinforce vocabulary and grammar skills in a format that students found enjoyable. Such practices illustrated how gamification enhances both learning outcomes and motivation. Further, the study aligned with Behera and Deb (2020), who highlighted the dual role of digital tools in enhancing classroom assessment and engagement. Participants explained how these tools provided immediate feedback and allowed for creative formative assessments. This encouraged students to

actively participated and gave teachers insight into learner progress. Their findings affirmed that digital strategies can support deeper learning and continuous instructional improvement. Furthermore, the study finds further supported in the work of Feng (2020), who emphasized the impact of technology on student behavior and participation through structured reward systems. Teachers shared that interactive platforms not only captured attention but also promoted discipline and cooperation during class activities. By integrating reward-based digital activities, they were able to maintain student focus and regulate classroom conduct. Feng’s research aligned with the observed benefits of combining instructional design with behavioral reinforcement.

3.3. *Values Drawn from the Study*—Adaptability and flexibility were essential qualities that enabled teachers to thrive in a constantly

evolving digital learning environment. As technology continues to shape education, teachers must be willing to adjusted their methods and

mindsets to keep pace with change. This adaptability promoted resilience and encourages a proactive approach to overcoming instructional challenges. Flexibility also allowed educators to modify their strategies to accommodate diverse learner needs, ensuring that teaching remains effective across various contexts. Creativity and innovation emerged as core values that empower educators to design engaging, meaningful learning experiences beyond traditional

3.3.1. Adaptability and Flexibility—Adaptability emerged as a central value among English teachers integrating instructional technology. They highlighted how swiftly adjusting to student needs, technology glitches, or shifting instructional tools was essential to teaching success. The ability to respond to challenges with composure and quick thinking reflects a mindset crucial for navigating the dynamic nature of tech-based instruction. Flexibility was not only applied to teaching methods but also in decision-making, lesson design, and resource use. These teachers recognized that no single tool or approach fits all students or scenarios, which strengthened their commitment to remain agile and open to continual learning and improvement. The findings of this study were consistent with Haleem et al. (2022), who found that teachers with adequate digital training exhibit greater adaptability and resilience in response to changing classroom dynamics. Participants in this study displayed similar qualities, adjusting their lesson plans, instructional materials, and pacing to accommodate both student needs and technological constraints. Their ability to pivot in response to challenges was often credited to the digital upskilling they pursued through webinars and workshops. This supported the notion that structured training is key to fostering digital confidence and instructional agility. In line with the work of Kormos (2022), this study also revealed that adaptability

methods. These attributes inspired teachers to experiment with digital tools, craft interactive lessons, and sustain learner interest despite virtual limitations. Furthermore, the emphasis on empathy and sensitivity underscores the importance of understanding learners' varied emotional, academic, and technological needs. By embracing individualized instruction, teachers reinforce inclusive education, ensuring no learner is left behind in the digital age.

is closely tied to teacher attitudes, cultural context, and the presence of institutional support. Participants described how their motivation to adopt flexible strategies was influenced by their belief in the benefits of technology and the encouragement they received from peers and administrators. Cultural expectations and access to collaborative environments played a significant role in shaping their instructional decisions. These factors underscore the complex interplay between internal mindset and external environment in shaping teacher adaptability. The findings further echo the conclusions of Banares (2020), who reported that teachers in rural areas must often employ flexible and creative teaching approaches due to inconsistent access to technology. In the current study, educators from resource-limited schools described modifying their delivery methods and relying on non-digital backups to ensure lesson continuity. These strategies included printed worksheets, rotational device usage, and offline tasks to bridge technological gaps. Such practices demonstrated how flexibility becomes a necessary survival skill in under-resourced educational contexts. Lastly, the study supported the insights of Alanoglu et al. (2022), who asserted that resilience and pedagogical innovation were cultivated through reflective teaching and intentional adaptation. Participants in this research frequently evaluated the effectiveness of their tech-integrated lessons and made adjust-

ments based on student feedback and classroom outcomes. This process of continual reflection allowed them to develop innovative ways of integrating digital tools despite external limitations.

3.3.2. Creativity and Innovation—Creativity was consistently emphasized as a core value, particularly when crafting visually appealing and interactive learning materials. Teachers noted that students' short attention spans required them to design engaging lessons using Canva, PowerPoint animations, and gamified applications. Innovation was not just about using tools but transforming content into meaningful, captivating learning experiences. These educators discovered the benefits of trying out new platforms and digital storytelling methods. Their willingness to innovate kept their teaching dynamic and aligned with learners' interests. As a result, their instruction stayed student-centered and relevant to today's educational landscape. Lee and Drajeti (2019) argued that ICT plays a significant role in fostering creativity within both teaching and learning processes. They particularly noted that digital tools enable educators to design original instructional materials that enhanced engagement and innovation. This study's participants reflected this perspective by creatively using platforms such as Canva, gamified presentations, and storytelling

3.3.3. Sensitivity to Learners' Needs and Individualized Instruction—Sensitivity to learners' needs and individualized instruction played a crucial role in the effective use of instructional technology, especially for English teachers. Through their experiences, many educators recognized that learners have varying levels of digital literacy, access to devices, and language proficiency. This awareness prompted them to design differentiated lessons that accommodate individual learning styles and chal-

Their experiences validated the importance of reflective practice in strengthening instructional resilience in digital learning environments.

to enrich their lessons. Abdullah et al. (2019) emphasized the evolving role of teachers, shifting from being mere deliverers of information to becoming digital facilitators who guide and supported learners in technology-enhanced environments. The participants' experiences in this study clearly echoed this transformation, demonstrating how they navigated this new role by integrating digital tools to enhanced learning. Also, Feng (2020) found that teachers can improve student learning by designing environments that integrate technology in ways that were both engaging and disciplined. This study supports Feng's findings, as participants described creating tech-enhanced classrooms that maintained structure while actively involving learners, thereby improving the overall learning experience. While, Layng (2023) highlighted the importance of tailoring instruction through innovative digital strategies to boost student motivation. This study confirmed Layng's observation, with participants reporting that their creative use of technology not only personalized learning but also significantly increased learners' enthusiasm and motivation.

lenges. By doing so, they created inclusive environments where all learners could participate and thrive, regardless of their starting point. English teachers also used technology to provide more personalized support, such as offering feedback through voice notes, one-on-one virtual sessions, or adaptive learning platforms. These strategies allowed teachers to address specific gaps in comprehension, writing skills, or vocabulary development. Moreover, technology enabled them to monitor progress more

closely and adjusted instruction based on real-time data. Such responsiveness -s a deeper empathy for learners, ensuring instruction is not only effective but also compassionate and learner-centered. Huang et al. (2020) emphasized that due to insufficient technical support, teachers often adopt self-help methods like on-line research or consulting tech-savvy peers to address device or software issues. These proactive behaviors demonstrated teachers' sensitivity to maintaining uninterrupted learning for their learners despite challenges. However, the lack of timely support causes lesson disruptions and lowers teachers' confidence in technology use, which negatively affects their ability to tailor instruction effectively. This barrier discourages experimentation with digital tools, limiting the personalization of instruction that could better meet diverse learner needs. Further, Tam (2020) highlighted the critical role of ongoing maintenance and timely technical support in sustaining a technology-enhanced learning environment. Consistent technical assistance helps minimize disruptions, enabling

teachers to focus on delivering lessons that can be adapted to individual learners' requirements. Without this support, technical difficulties interfere with technology integration, reducing the potential to customize instruction based on learner differences. Hence, effective technical infrastructure is essential for teachers to be responsive and sensitive to the diverse needs of their learners. Furthermore, Zheng et al. (2022) reported that many teachers address gaps in formal training by engaging in self-directed learning and peer collaboration to improved their technology skills. This initiative reflects teachers' awareness and sensitivity toward enhancing their instructional strategies to better serve learners' individual needs. Nonetheless, the absence of structured professional development focused on practical classroom technology used leaves many educators feeling underprepared. This lack of formal training limits teachers' capacity to implement individualized instruction through digital tools, affecting their responsiveness to learners' unique learning styles and needs.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, drawing out implications from this study is anchored in the authentic, lived experiences of English teachers navigating instructional technology in a real-world classroom setting.

4.1. Findings—Their narratives provided a clear picture of the evolving role of educators from struggling with limited digital literacy to becoming adaptive, reflective, and student-centered practitioners. Understanding these transitions is essential, as it revealed not only what challenges exist, but how teachers respond creatively and practically to systemic gaps. These responses serve as a critical foundation for shaping educational policies, professional development programs, and institutional reforms that genuinely reflect ground-level realities. Moreover, the narratives col-

lected emphasized that successful technology integration cannot be addressed through infrastructure alone it requires relational, contextual, and values-driven approaches. Teachers' actions were shaped by mentorship, collaboration, and the feedback of their students, which underscores the social and emotional dimensions of instructional change. By translating these findings into actionable implications, the study offers insights that extend beyond individual classrooms and into broader educational frameworks. This rationale ensured that the implications presented were not theoretical gener-

Fig. 5. Values drawn from the study

alizations but grounded recommendations that directly emerged from what the participants experienced, practiced, and learned.

4.2. *Implications*—The findings of the study emphasized the essential need for technology integration in education to be grounded in pedagogical intent rather than novelty. Teachers revealed that their gradual adoption of digital tools became more effective when aligned with specific learning outcomes in English instruction. This suggested that instructional technology should not merely supplement lessons but serve as an intentional extension of classroom goals to maximize learner engagement and comprehension. The role of continuous professional development emerged as a crucial factor in enhancing teachers’ confidence and competence in using technology. Participants reported that workshops, mentorship, and collaboration with colleagues, significantly shaped their instructional practices. These insights imply that teacher training programs must prioritize context-based, experiential learning op-

portunities that equip educators with adaptable, real-world strategies aligned with Distributed Cognitive Theory (Hutchin,1990). Equally significant is the implication that institutional and leadership support greatly influence the success of technology integration in schools. Teachers who experienced encouragement and flexibility from school heads were more empowered to experiment and innovate in their classrooms. Hence, school administrators must take an active role in providing moral, technical, and logistical backing to create a culture of digital innovation. Teachers’ coping strategies reflected a strong sense of adaptability and resilience, especially in addressing technological limitations and diverse learner needs. The frequent use of backup plans, peer-assisted learning, and differentiated activities highlighted their strategic approach to ensure instructional continuity anchored with Technology Pedagogical Content

Knowledge (TPACK) Model (Mishra Koehler, 2006). This points to the need for systemic recognition and support of teachers' adaptive competencies as essential elements of effective instructional design. The findings of the study also revealed that values such as perseverance, humility, and learner centered became more evident as teachers navigated digital transitions supported by technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989). These values played a significant role in shaping how they approached challenges and supported their students. The im-

plication is that technology integration must be coupled with character-building initiatives to sustain meaningful educational change. Finally, the reliance on student feedback to improved technology use reflects the evolving teacher-learner dynamic in digital classrooms. Teachers became more responsive and reflective practitioners by involving learners in the instructional process. This underscores the importance of fostering participatory learning environments where student voices help shape teaching strategies.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the study's findings, it is crucial that the results were effectively communicated and utilized by the key individuals for whom this research was designed.

Teachers.

English teachers should be given continued opportunities for hands-on professional development, particularly on how to integrate instructional technology in context-sensitive ways. The findings showed that when teachers engaged in peer mentoring, self-paced learning, and collaborative dialogue, their confidence and competence improved. Future efforts must supported teacher-led innovation through professional learning communities, time for reflection, and recognition of adaptive practices. Empowering teachers to share best practices within and across schools can drive sustainable growth in digital integration.

Principals.

School heads should take a more proactive role as instructional technology leaders by creating an enabling environment for innovation. Participants emphasized the importance of school-provided tools and logistical support in facilitating effective digital instruction. Future directions should include providing principals with training on digital leadership, coaching models, and flexible resource allocation. En-

couraging collaboration between teachers and school heads will foster mutual accountability and shared ownership of technology-driven initiatives.

Department of Education (DepEd).

DepEd should institutionalize responsive policies that support localized technology integration. Teachers in the study expressed a strong need for equitable access to tools, continuous training, and sustainable support systems. Moving forward, DepEd should prioritize investments in infrastructure for remote and under-resourced schools and ensured that digital tools aligned with pedagogical goals. Furthermore, guidelines for implementing school-based technology plans should be co-developed with teachers to ensured practicality and sustainability.

Future Researchers.

The study opens new avenues for deeper exploration into technology integration in English teaching from diverse lenses. Future researchers may explore comparative studies between rural and urban school divisions, or investigate how student achievement correlates with teacher digital competence. Longitudinal studies that track the professional growth of teachers engaged in continuous tech-integration would also be valuable. Moreover, research on learner feedback loops and student-led technology adaptation could shed light on how to further personalize

and optimize instruction.

Learners

Learners play a vital role in shaping how technology is used in English instruction. As teachers reported, student engagement increased when technology was interactive and student-centered. Future programs should equip

learners with digital literacy skills that empower them not only to access content but to participate in co creating classroom activities. Encouraging students to provide feedback on digital tools and lesson formats can strengthen participatory learning and ensure instruction remains responsive to their needs.

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